

The value of a climate march: Do climate marches affect perceived values and personal climate action

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Abstract

Climate change poses immediate environmental threats. Although many care about the environment (i.e., endorse biospheric values), too little climate action is still taken. It has been argued that one reason for this is that individuals often underestimate others' biospheric values, which demotivates them to act. We propose that climate marches have the potential to prevent and correct such underestimation by making a group of climate marchers with strong biospheric values salient and increasing awareness of the widespread endorsement of biospheric values among national citizens. To investigate this, we studied personal biospheric values, perceived biospheric values of climate marchers and national citizens, and individuals' engagement in climate action just before and after a large climate march in the Netherlands, among a sample that was aimed to be national representative (valid $n_{T1} = 648$, $n_{T2} = 502$). Individuals reported themselves and climate marchers to have strong biospheric values, while national citizens were seen as having substantially weaker biospheric values. Multiple regression analyses indicated stronger personal biospheric values and stronger perceived biospheric values of climate marchers – but seemingly weaker perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens – were associated to stronger climate action engagement. Perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens did increase over the march, whereas perceived biospheric values of climate marchers decreased. Individuals did not engage in more climate action over the climate march, as one the abovementioned associations already suggested. We argue that such effects may occur in the longer term in contexts where the national identity is more salient and relevant.

Introduction

Climate change poses significant threats to ecosystems and societies worldwide. To mitigate climate change, wide-ranging climate action is needed, which includes climate mitigative behaviours of individual citizens and their support for climate policies¹. Notably, most individuals appear motivated to engage in climate action, as indicated by their strong endorsement of biospheric values (i.e., caring about nature and society)²⁻⁴. Even though individuals do translate these values into climate action⁴⁻⁷, the level to which this occurs is too little and too inconsistent to limit global warming below the necessary 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels¹. Why is this the case, and what can be done about it?

One reason why individuals do not consistently act on their personal biospheric values is that they are also influenced by what they perceive others to value (i.e., perceived group values or second-order beliefs)^{8,9}. Many individuals underestimate others' endorsement of biospheric values, thinking that others are relatively self-interested and care less about nature, others and society than they do^{8,10-14}. This underestimation of others' biospheric values can discourage individuals from taking climate action⁹, for instance, causing them to believe that climate action is little appreciated, inefficacious and not sensible to do^{11,15,16}. To promote climate action, it is therefore essential to know whether and how these underestimations can change^{8,17}.

We argue that underestimations of others' biospheric values partly arise because people seldomly talk about, nor publicly share, their personal values^{8,17,18}. We aim to investigate whether such underestimations may reduce when people *en masse* speak up about caring for nature and society^{3,17}. Specifically, we argue that large-scale climate marches in which many different people participate could signal to individuals that many people do care about nature and the environment, thus making the widespread—but often unnoticed—endorsement of biospheric values more visible. We will explore how individuals' climate action engagement is associated with their perceived endorsement of biospheric values of climate marchers and national citizens over the course of a climate march and discuss the short- and long-term consequences climate marches may have on individuals' climate actions.

Personal Values as Motivators of Climate Action

Many studies identify personal values as key motivators of individuals' beliefs and actions^{19–22}, including climate action^{5,7,23,24}. Personal values are defined as general and desirable life goals that people strive for in their lives. Values are relatively stable over time and contexts and are used as guiding principles where individuals base their choices and behaviours on^{25–27}. A comprehensive list of universal values has been identified, each of which is endorsed to at least some degree by every individual across the world^{6,26,27}. The values that an individual endorses more strongly exert more influence over their choices and behaviours and are more decisive in what actions an individual will take^{19,26,27}.

When focusing on climate action, biospheric values are particularly relevant^{2,4,5}. Biospheric values reflect the degree to which an individual cares about nature and the environment^{23,28}. Since mitigating climate change has clear benefits for nature and the environment, individuals with stronger biospheric values are typically more motivated and likely to engage in climate action^{2,4,5}. Accordingly, the more strongly individuals endorse biospheric values, the more they engage in climate action (**Hypothesis 1**).

Group Values as Motivators of Climate Action

Next to being motivated to act according to one's personal values, it has recently been found that individuals are also motivated to act in line with the values of others, or better said: what they *perceive* others to value^{9,11,13,29}. Our perceptions of others' values inform us about what others may approve or desire. Individuals may therefore act on others' values to maintain or gain social approval, which is essential since humans are social beings and depend on others for their survival¹⁵. Moreover, individuals may engage in behaviours that align with the values of desirable groups, signalling to others that they belong to that group and gaining social status^{30,31}. The perceived values of others may also inform individuals about what actions are worth pursuing, particularly if those actions depend on others and serve collective interests. This may strongly apply to climate action, as climate action mainly serves

collective benefits, which will only be achieved when many people take action^{8,10,11}. Furthermore, if an individual sympathises or identifies with a group of others, the individual may regard the values of those others as personally relevant and meaningful. This may intrinsically motivate the individual to consistently act according to those values^{9,30,32,33}.

When translating these insights into the current study context of climate change, individuals who perceive others to have stronger biospheric values are likely more inclined to take climate action. Indeed, individuals engaged more in climate action when they perceived the endorsement of biospheric values to be stronger among fellow national citizens, similar voters⁹, fellow university students¹³, and fellow school pupils¹⁴. From this, we hypothesise that the stronger individuals perceive others to endorse biospheric values, the more they engage in climate action (**Hypothesis 2**).

Differences in (Perceived) Biospheric Value Endorsement

When looking at individuals' personal endorsement of values, most people report strongly endorsing biospheric values^{3,29}. In fact, many people prioritise biospheric values over most other values, including hedonic values (i.e., caring about pleasure and gratification of one's desires) and, in particular, egoistic values (i.e., caring about possessions, status and power), two values that typically demotivate climate action²⁴. This is true across people from different countries, demographics (e.g., income and education levels) and political leanings³⁴. Hence, many people appear personally motivated to take climate action, even though this does not always manifest in practice^{3,4,29}.

Interestingly, individuals see most others to have weaker biospheric values than measures of personal biospheric values suggest^{8,11,12,35}, for related findings see: ,36–39. This pattern is consistent across different groups, including national citizens, colleagues, classmates, and friends^{9,11,14,37–39}.

When combining these insights with the findings and hypotheses presented earlier, there seems to be a strong value basis for climate action at the personal level but a substantially weaker perceived value basis for climate action by others. The latter may significantly deter individuals from taking climate action and can be a crucial factor that should be addressed to achieve substantial progress in promoting climate action^{3,4,29}. Accordingly, this paper focuses on whether underestimating others' biospheric values can be prevented or corrected.

Addressing (Mis)perceptions of Others' Biospheric Values to Promote Climate Action

To understand whether and how underestimations of others' biospheric values can be prevented or changed to promote climate action, it is essential to comprehend what these perceptions reflect and where they come from. Overall, there appears to be a scientific consensus that these perceptions – at least to a substantial degree – reflect a structural underestimation of others' biospheric values or others' morality more generally^{4,8,11,29,35,37}. Individuals often do not know what others value because people

hardly talk about this publicly^{8,17,18}. Individuals, therefore, often infer others' values from the behaviours they see them take and the information they receive about them, which are, however, often negatively biased^{8,11,17,40}. For example, despite the widespread support and participation in climate action, behaviours contributing to climate change tend to be more visible⁴⁰⁻⁴², more widely discussed (e.g., in media)^{40,42-45}, and more frequently attributed to others' intrinsic dispositions rather than external circumstances (i.e. fundamental attribution error)^{46,47}. This often leads to the overly pessimistic perception that most others care less about nature and the environment than others actually do.

Whereas, following Hypothesis 2, these underestimations of others' biospheric values may discourage individuals from engaging in climate action, the abovementioned reasoning also implies that when a group would visibly engage in climate action and communicate their caring for the environment, such underestimations of biospheric values are less likely to occur. There is some initial support for this proposition among clearly environmental groups, such as climate activists and green political parties, whose biospheric values appear to be less underestimated and sometimes even overestimated⁹. In such instances, that group's perceived endorsement of biospheric values may promote, rather than weaken, climate action among individuals.

Climate Marches and Perceived Biospheric Values

In this light, large-scale climate marches may be relevant and influential in promoting climate action via the perceived biospheric value of two groups. First, during climate marches, a vocal and clear environmental group of "climate marchers" is likely salient and relevant, which is likely perceived as having strong biospheric values, and may accordingly motivate individuals to take climate action. Second, if many different people attend a climate march, this may be seen as reflecting the voice of a substantial part of the national population, possibly causing people to update their perceptions about national citizens. Specifically, national citizens may be perceived as endorsing biospheric values more strongly after than before the climate march, which could further stimulate climate action. We discuss these points, which are the core propositions of our paper, in more detail below.

Perceptions of Climate Marchers' Biospheric Values

Climate marches often reflect large-scale collective climate action, in which climate marchers publicly indicate their concerns about climate change and support for climate action, and urge governments and organisations to take climate action. Because climate marchers visibly engage in climate action and explicitly communicate pro-environmental goals, it appears likely that most individuals will acknowledge that climate marchers have strong biospheric values⁸. Accordingly, when a climate march occurs, the group of climate marchers likely becomes relevant and salient to many individuals, who likely perceive them as having relatively strong biospheric values.

As most people strongly endorse biospheric values^{3,4,29,48}, many will at least sympathise with climate marchers' goals and ambitions and be potentially inspired by the underlying values that drive marchers.

Furthermore, experiencing that a large and diverse group of climate marchers is motivated to take climate action may make individuals feel more efficacious, empowering them to take climate action^{8,11}. Accordingly, specifying our earlier Hypothesis 2 to the group of climate marchers, we hypothesise that the stronger individuals perceive climate marchers to endorse biospheric values, the more they engage in climate action (**Hypothesis 2a**).

Perceptions of National Citizens' Biospheric Values

In contrast to climate marchers, national citizens are generally perceived to have weaker biospheric values than is the case, which was found to deter individuals from climate action^{9,13,38,39}. However, these underestimations may decrease over a climate march. At climate marches, substantial groups of national citizens show their concern about climate change and the current level of climate action and, thereby, their strong biospheric values. This may break the typical silence surrounding personal values that cause underestimations, signalling that more national citizens strongly endorse biospheric values than many might have initially thought. Accordingly, we hypothesise that the general underestimation of national citizens' endorsement of biospheric values will decrease throughout the climate march, meaning that the perceived biospheric values of national citizens will be higher after than before a climate march (**Hypothesis 3**). This, in turn, may have the downstream consequence that individuals intensify their climate action if they indeed act in line with the values they perceive others to endorse, as previous research suggested (**Hypothesis 2b**).

Methods

We tested our hypotheses with data we collected around a climate march held in the Netherlands, which attracted about 40,000 climate marchers and was covered widely in the national media (e.g., headlined newspapers, prime-time television and radio coverage, and social media). We designed a two-wave longitudinal study to fulfil multiple research purposes, for which we gathered data on values, perceptions, beliefs, attitudes and actions. The study was pre-registered with and approved by the ethical committee of [REMOVED FOR BLIND REVIEW].

Data collection and sample

Data was collected in two waves, T1 and T2, among a sample that aimed to be representative of the Dutch population. T1 occurred in the four days before the climate march, and T2 occurred between days nine and eighteen after the climate march. Respondents were recruited via the Dutch panel provider "thesistoolspro" and were selected to be representative in terms of gender, age and education for the Dutch population. We asked the panel provider to aim for around 800 respondents, which would result in sufficient power for the diverse research purposes for which the data was collected, and to stop T1 data collection at midnight before the climate march took place. Respondents were compensated for their

time with a €1.00 voucher for a large webshop. In total, 827 respondents were recruited to participate in the study, of which 616 started both the T1 and T2 questionnaires.

Data quality was inspected based on three criteria. First, we identified and removed respondents with unrealistic inconsistencies in their responses within or across time points. Specifically, we removed respondents who (i) indicated that they did not believe in climate change but also to be strongly worried about it, (ii) believed that climate change has positive impacts but also to be strongly worried about it, (iii) who reported unrealistic changes on variables between the two waves of data collection (e.g., gender change, becoming younger, or multiple years older). Second, we removed respondents with missing data on the focal variables of our analyses (i.e., predictors or outcome variables). Third, we removed respondents who finished the questionnaire in less than 30% of the Median response time, which was below 258 seconds for T1 and below 148 seconds for T2.

Based on these criteria, we removed 84 respondents for data inconsistencies and 95 for having missing data (37 of which were also considered speeders) at T1. We removed 80 respondents for data inconsistencies, 27 for having missing data (14 of which were also considered speeders), and 1 for speeding at T2. This left us with 648 valid responses at T1 (54% male; $M_{\text{age}} = 54.2$ years, $SD_{\text{age}} = 15.3$) and 502 valid responses that completed both T1 and T2 (55% male; $M_{\text{age}} = 55.1$ years, $SD_{\text{age}} = 15.1$) of which 20 attended the climate march^[1].

With these sample sizes, posthoc sensitivity power analyses indicated that we would be able to detect small-sized effects of $f^2 = 0.03$ in a multiple regression model with three predictors with a Type 1 error probability of 0.05 and a power of 0.95 (Hypotheses 1 and 2); and a small-sized effect of $d_z = 0.16$ in a within-subjects repeated measures analysis with a Type 1 error probability of 0.05, and power of 0.95 (Hypotheses 3).

Procedure

After signing up for our study on the panel provider's website, respondents were directed to our T1 questionnaire programmed in Qualtrics. Respondents were first presented with informed consent, where – after approval – demographic questions (gender, age) were asked, followed by measures of personal values and climate beliefs. After that, respondents were informed that a climate march was scheduled for the upcoming Sunday and asked to indicate what they perceived the values and climate beliefs of fellow Dutch citizens and climate marchers to be, respectively, followed by items on the level of identification with these groups and some questions on attitudes towards and expectations about the climate march. Finally, questions were asked about the extent to which respondents are likely to engage in different types of climate action.

Nine days after the climate march, respondents of T1 were invited to participate in the T2 questionnaire, which started with questions about the climate march and climate marchers (i.e., attendance, emotions, knowledge, attitudes, values, and identification with climate marchers). After that, questions were asked

about Dutch citizens (perceived climate beliefs, values, identification with Dutch citizens), followed by questions about the respondents themselves (i.e., environmental self-identity, policy support, climate action intentions, climate beliefs and demographics).

All variables were presented in the order discussed above, while within multi-item scales, the items were presented in random order. The full questionnaires and the data used for this study are available here [anonymised link for review – will be updated after acceptance]. The variables relevant to this study are personal biospheric values, perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens and climate marchers, and individuals' climate action engagement. These were all measured at both time points and are discussed in more detail below under materials.

Materials

Biospheric values. We measured the personal biospheric values and the perceived values of national citizens and climate marchers with an adaptation of the Environmental Value Questionnaire (E-PVQ)⁴⁹ developed by Kelly and colleagues (2023). We used this adapted version of the E-PVQ because it measures the four values most relevant to climate action (i.e., biospheric, altruistic, egoistic, hedonic), each with one instead of multiple items (e.g., three to five items per value in the E-PVQ). This was necessary because we had to ask for each value six times (i.e., for personal values, perceived national values, and perceived climate march values at both time points), making it infeasible to use the standard, extensive value questionnaires such as the E-PVQ. Despite the obvious shortcomings of a single-item measure, the measure seems to capture the values well, with single value items correlating strongly ($r_s > 0.76$) with the respective composite value score on the more extensive E-PVQ¹⁴.

Respondents' personal endorsement of biospheric values was measured by asking about their agreement with the statement "I find it extremely important in life to respect nature and protect the environment" on a 7-point scale (1 *completely disagree* to 7 *completely agree*). For the perceived endorsement of biospheric values by Dutch citizens and climate marchers, similar statements were used, but with "I find" being replaced by respectively "I think that the average Dutch citizen finds" and "I think that the average climate marcher finds". We used the raw score of each item in our analyses[2]. Since we measured the items at both T1 and T2, we inspected the internal consistency of each item, which was fair for personal biospheric values ($r_{T1-T2} = .58$) and perceived biospheric values of climate marchers ($r_{T1-T2} = .41$) but substantially weaker for perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens ($r_{T1-T2} = .29$). However, these low to fair consistency levels are not surprising given that we anticipated changes in perceived values over time.

Climate action engagement was measured with three subscales: i) private pro-environmental behaviour engagement, (ii) public pro-environmental behaviour engagement, and (iii) climate policy support, which we treated and analysed as three separate outcome variables.

Private pro-environmental behaviour engagement (Private PEB) was measured with five statements, where respondents had to indicate to what extent these statements were true for them personally (1 *not true at all* to 7 *completely true*). These items were “I try to use as little energy as possible (e.g. by lowering the heating, showering shortly, switching off appliances that are not in use)”, “I try to primarily use energy from renewable sources (e.g., wind, solar) instead of fossil sources (e.g. coal, gas)”, “I try to use energy smartly, meaning I adjust my energy use to the supply of sustainably generated energy (e.g., use electricity when the sun shines)”, “I try to walk or cycle when travelling short distances (< 15 km), rather than using motorised ways of transport”, “I try to use sustainable modes of transport (e.g., public transport, electric vehicle, long-distance trains) for longer distances (> 50 km) instead of using higher emitting modes of transport (e.g. petrol car, aeroplane).” The scale showed acceptable reliability ($\alpha_{T1} = .68$; $\alpha_{T2} = .68$) and high internal consistency over the timepoint ($r_{T1-T2} = .83$); therefore, a composite score was created by calculating the average score over the items, which is used in the analysis.

Public pro-environmental behaviour engagement (Public PEB) was measured with descriptions of climate actions in a given (social) context, for which respondents had to indicate how likely it was they would participate in them (1 *very unlikely* to 7 *very likely*). These items were: “If people come over for dinner, how likely are you to serve them a vegetarian dish?” “When someone clearly acts in an environmentally harmful way (e.g., taking the car instead of a bicycle for a short distance), how likely is it that you will say something about this to this person?” “How likely is it that you will talk with friends, colleagues, and/or neighbours about sustainable ways of living (e.g., energy saving, reducing meat consumption, sustainable investments).” The scale showed acceptable reliability ($\alpha_{T1} = .66$; $\alpha_{T2} = .67$) and high internal consistency over the timepoint ($r_{T1-T2} = .84$); therefore, a composite score was created by calculating the average score over the items, which is used in the analysis.

Climate policy support. Respondents indicated their support for seven different climate policies: “Using governmental money to subsidise solar- and wind energy”, “Implementing regulations to ban the least energy efficient household appliances”; “Large-scale expansion of renewable energy production (e.g., large wind farms and solar fields)”; “Tax based on CO₂ emissions (carbon tax). Those who emit more CO₂, pay more tax”; “Substantially increase prices of flying”; “Substantially increase prices of meat”; “Regulations that force homeowners to make their houses more energy efficient”. For each climate policy, respondents indicated the degree to which they found this policy acceptable or not on a 6-point scale (1 *very unacceptable* to 6 *very acceptable*). The scale showed good reliability ($\alpha_{T1} = .85$; $\alpha_{T2} = .85$) and high internal consistency over the timepoint ($r_{T1-T2} = .88$); therefore, a composite score was created by calculating the average score over the items, which is used in the analysis.

Results

Descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows the means and standard deviations of the relevant measures at T1 (the full T1 sample and the subsample who also completed T2) and T2. In line with earlier research, respondents indicated

very strong agreement with the statement that they find it extremely important in life to respect nature and protect the environment, reflecting a strong endorsement of biospheric values across all (sub)samples and both time points.

Also, in line with earlier research, Dutch citizens were generally perceived to endorse biospheric values much weaker than respondents themselves ($ps < .001$). Climate marchers were perceived to endorse biospheric values slightly stronger than respondents themselves at T1 ($p = 0.06$ in the full sample, $p = 0.37$ in the T1 subsample) but weaker than respondents themselves at T2 ($p = .004$).

Table 1 Descriptive statistics for the main variables of our study.

	T1 (full sample)		T1 (subsample who also completed T2)		T2 sample (who also completed T1)	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Pers. bio. values	6.22	0.86	6.27	0.79	6.16	0.81
Perc. bio. values NL	4.51	1.27	4.51	1.28	4.99	1.07
Perc. bio. values CM	6.34	0.94	6.37	0.89	6.01	1.09
Private PEB	4.31	1.25	4.32	1.24	4.31	1.20
Public PEB	3.25	1.45	3.26	1.44	3.30	1.38
Climate policy support	4.13	1.10	4.19	1.09	4.10	1.05

Note.

Table 2 shows that higher scores on personal biospheric values were associated with higher scores on personal pro-environmental engagement, public pro-environmental engagement, and climate policy support, which supports Hypothesis 1. Similarly, individuals who indicated climate marchers endorsed biospheric values more strongly generally scored higher on private pro-environmental engagement, public pro-environmental engagement, and climate policy support, supporting Hypothesis 2a. Perceived endorsement of biospheric values by national citizens was not significantly associated with private pro-environmental behaviour engagement, and was even negatively correlated with public pro-environmental engagement and climate policy support. This means that individuals who perceive Dutch citizens to endorse biospheric values more strongly were generally less likely to engage in public pro-environmental behaviour and to support climate policy, which is not in line with earlier studies and Hypothesis 2b.

Table 2 Bivariate Pearson correlation coefficients of personal biospheric values (pers. bio. values), perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens (perc. bio. values NL), perceived biospheric values of climate marchers (perc. bio values CM), with private pro-environmental behaviour engagement (Priv. PEB), public pro-environmental behaviour engagement (Public PEB) and climate policy support in each (sub)sample.

	T1 (full sample)			T1 (subsample who also completed T2)			T2 (who also completed T1)		
	Priv. PEB	Public PEB	Policy support	Priv. PEB	Public PEB	Policy support	Priv. PEB	Public PEB	Policy support
Pers. values	.25***	.27***	.34***	.23***	.26***	.36***	.27***	.33***	.40***
Perc. bio values NL	-.06	-.10**	-.15***	-.08	-.12**	-.18***	-.05	-.11*	-.06
Perc. bio values CM	.14***	.22***	.30***	.09*	.19***	.31***	.24***	.33***	.41***

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Notably, only neglectable differences were observed between the bivariate correlation coefficients of the full T1 sample and the T1 subsample, suggesting that drop-out between T1 and T2 did not substantially bias our sample on the measures relevant to our study. In addition, the general patterns of correlations at T1 were mostly replicated at T2, showing that the directions of the relationships were stable across time points. In the following sections, we will first test the hypothesised relationships between (perceived) biospheric values and pro-environmental action (Hypotheses 1 and 2) in more detail. After that, we will continue with analysing differences between T1 and T2 in terms of (a) scores on (perceived) value endorsement and pro-environmental engagement (Hypothesis 3) and (b) relationships between (perceived) biospheric values and pro-environmental action.

The relationship between (perceived) values and pro-environmental action

To examine to what extent personal and perceived group values are uniquely related to climate action engagement, multiple regression analyses were performed for T1 (see Table 3) and T2 (see Table 4), which included all (perceived) biospheric values at the timepoint as predictor variables, and all climate action engagement variables at the timepoint as outcome variables. For T1, which we report first, we ran the regression analysis for the full sample and the subsample of respondents who also filled in T2. For T2, on which we report after that, we ran a regression with all predictors at T2 and one controlling for the T1 measure of each respective outcome variable (i.e., private pro-environmental behaviour, public pro-environmental behaviour, climate policy support), which could be considered a highly conservative test of our Hypotheses. Notably, it can be expected that the engagement in climate action at T2 is very strongly predicted by the engagement in climate action a few weeks earlier (T1) since people tend to be

rather consistent in their actions and answers, leaving little unexplained variance (perceived) biospheric values could predict. Moreover, climate action engagement at T1 is likely also associated with (perceived) biospheric values, meaning that a lot of the variance that (perceived) biospheric values could explain in climate action engagement at T2 is already captured by the T1 climate action engagement measure.

Table 3 shows that each (perceived) biospheric value is substantially uniquely associated with different climate actions. Generally, the stronger individuals endorsed biospheric values themselves, and the stronger they perceived climate marchers to endorse biospheric values, the more they generally engaged in climate action. Importantly, personal biospheric values and perceived biospheric values of climate marchers both explained unique variance in almost every action, except for private pro-environmental behaviour engagement in the T1 subsample. The perceived endorsement of biospheric values by Dutch citizens remained negatively related to engagement in almost all climate actions, except for private pro-environmental behaviour engagement in the full T1 sample. This means that the more individuals perceived Dutch citizens to endorse biospheric values, the less they engaged in climate action, also when we control for other personal biospheric values and the perceived biospheric values of climate marchers. Again, patterns and coefficients were highly similar between the full and subsample at T1, suggesting little biases due to drop-out between time points.

Table 3 Standardised regression coefficients of multiple regression analyses with personal biospheric values (pers. bio. values), perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens (perc. bio. values NL) and perceived biospheric values of climate marchers (perc. bio. values CM) as predictors of private pro-environmental behaviour engagement (personal PEB), public pro-environmental behaviour engagement (public PEB) and climate policy support for the T1 full sample (top) and the T1 subsample of those respondents that also completed T2 (bottom).

	Private PEB			Public PEB			Policy support		
	β	95%CI		β	95%CI		β	95%CI	
Full T1 sample (n = 648)									
Pers. bio values	.23*	.15	.31	.23*	.16	.31	.28*	.21	.35
Perc. bio values NL	-.06	-.14	.01	-.11*	-.18	-.03	-.16*	-.23	-.09
Perc. bio values CM	.09*	.02	.17	.18*	.10	.25	.24*	.17	.32
	$F(3,644) = 17.14,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .07$			$F(3,644) = 27.27,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .11$			$F(3,644) = 50.36,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .19$		
T1 subsample (n = 502)									
Pers. bio values	.22*	.13	.30	.24*	.15	.32	.31*	.23	.39
Perc. bio values NL	-.09*	-.17	.00	-.13*	-.21	-.05	-.19*	-.26	-.11
Perc. bio values CM	.05	-.04	.14	.14*	.06	.23	.25*	.17	.33
	$F(3,498) = 10.84,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .06$			$F(3,498) = 19.53,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .11$			$F(3,498) = 47.79,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .22$		

Note. * $p < .05$

Table 2 shows that all (perceived) biospheric values also uniquely contributed to explaining climate action engagement at T2. As observed at T1, individuals who scored higher on personal biospheric values and perceived biospheric values of climate marchers also scored higher on private pro-environmental behaviour engagement, public pro-environmental behaviour engagement and climate policy support, even when controlling for scores on the respective climate actions at T1 (although the unique effects of (perceived) values became small). This strongly supports Hypotheses 1 and 2, respectively. Individuals who scored higher on perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens scored lower on private pro-environmental behaviour engagement, public pro-environmental behaviour engagement and climate policy support when not controlling for scores on the respective climate actions at T1, which was similar to what we found at T1 but not in line with Hypothesis 2b. However,

these effects became statistically non-significant when controlling for the respective climate action at T1.

Table 4 Standardised regression coefficients of multiple regression analyses with personal biospheric values (pers. bio. values), perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens (perc. bio. values NL) and perceived biospheric values of climate marchers (perc. bio. values CM) as predictors of personal pro-environmental behaviour engagement (personal PEB), public pro-environmental behaviour engagement (public PEB) and climate policy support policy support at T2, without (top) and with (bottom) controlling for scores on the respective behaviour at T1.

	Personal PEB			Public PEB			Policy support		
	β	95%CI		β	95%CI		β	95%CI	
Pers. bio values	.23*	.15	.32	.29*	.21	.38	.33*	.25	.41
Perc. bio values NL	-.12*	-.21	-.04	-.21*	-.29	-.13	-.18*	-.26	-.10
Perc. bio values CM	.20*	.11	.28	.27*	.19	.36	.34*	.27	.42
	$F(3,644) = 21.99,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .12$			$F(3,644) = 44.04,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .21$			$F(3,644) = 65.63,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .28$		
	Personal PEB			Public PEB			Policy support		
Pers. bio values	.06*	.01	.11	.09*	.03	.14	.09*	.04	.13
Perc. bio values NL	-.03	-.08	.02	-.04	-.09	.01	-.04	-.08	.00
Perc. bio values CM	.07*	.02	.12	.06*	.01	.11	.06*	.02	.11
T1 – Personal PEB, Public PEB, Policy support	.80*	.75	.85	.79*	.73	.84	.82*	.78	.87
	$F(4,497) = 285.44,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .69$			$F(4,497) = 863.92,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .71$			$F(4,497) = 1175.11,$ $p < .001, R^2 = .79$		

Note. * $p < .05$

Do means and associations change throughout a climate march?

Finally, we tested whether the earlier presented means and associations changed throughout the climate march. Table 5 shows that, in line with our Hypothesis 3, we observed a medium-sized increase in how much Dutch citizens were perceived to endorse biospheric values. Further explorative analyses indicated a small-sized decrease in personal biospheric values and a small to medium-sized decrease in perceived endorsement of biospheric values by climate marchers (likely because of finding out that the climate

march was more mainstream than anticipated, see discussion). Furthermore, a small decrease in policy acceptance was found, whereas scores on the other climate actions did not change over time.

Table 5 Differences between the T1 subsample and T2 on mean scores for (perceived) value scores and climate action engagement. Positive changes indicate that the score increased over time, whereas negative changes indicate that the score decreased over time.

	ΔM	95%CI LB	95%CI UB	$t(501)$	p	Cohen's d
Pers. bio values	-.11	-.17	-.04	-3.20	.001	-.14
Perc. bio values NL	.48	.35	.60	7.53	<.001	.34
Perc. bio values CM	-.35	-.45	-.26	-7.29	<.001	-.33
Private PEB	-.01	-.07	.05	-.33	.745	-.01
Public PEB	.05	-.02	.12	1.34	.179	.06
Climate policy support	-.09	-.14	-.05	-4.06	<.001	-.18

We further conducted explorative analyses with the *cocor* R package by Diedenhofen & Much⁵⁰ to test whether associations between (perceived) biospheric values and climate actions significantly changed over time (see Table 6). The positive correlations between the perceived biospheric values of climate marchers and all climate actions grew significantly stronger over the course of the climate march. The positive correlations between personal biospheric values and climate actions did not significantly change over the course of the climate march, and neither did the negative correlations between perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens and private and public pro-environmental behaviour engagement change over time. The negative correlation between perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens and climate policy acceptance did, however, significantly change, decreasing in strength over time and, thus, becoming less negatively correlated.

Table 6 Differences between the T1 subsample and T2 on Pearson's absolute correlations for (perceived) value scores and climate action engagement. Positive changes reflect a strengthening of the positive/negative correlation over time, whereas negative changes reflect a weakening of the positive/negative correlation.

	Δr	z	p	95%CI LB	95%CI UB
Pers. bio values with					
Private PEB	.04	0.94	.350	.04	-.13
Public PEB	.06	1.61	.107	.01	-.15
Climate policy support	.03	0.09	.395	.04	-.11
Perc. bio values NL with					
Private PEB	-.04	-0.06	.526	-.14	.07
Public PEB	-.02	-0.29	.770	-.12	.09
Climate policy support	-.12	-2.13	.033	-.22	-.01
Perc. bio values CM with					
Private PEB	.15	3.02	.003	.05	.24
Public PEB	.14	2.84	.005	.04	.23
Climate policy support	.10	2.24	.024	.01	.19

Discussion

Our findings offer clear support for most of our hypotheses. Individuals indicated that they strongly endorsed biospheric values and perceived climate marchers as doing so as well. Individuals perceived Dutch citizens to endorse biospheric values substantially less than themselves and climate marchers. Stronger personal biospheric values and stronger perceived biospheric values of climate marchers were associated with stronger engagement in different climate action engagement, supporting respectively **Hypothesis 1 and 2a**. **Hypothesis 2b** was not supported: individuals who perceived Dutch citizens to have stronger biospheric values did not engage in more – and according to some analyses, even in less – climate action. When inspecting changes over the course of the climate march, we observed that the perceived endorsement of biospheric values by Dutch citizens did increase, supporting **Hypothesis 3**. Only small differences were observed in personal values and climate action engagement across timepoints. Interestingly, the perceived endorsement of biospheric values by climate marchers seemed to decrease over time, while the strength of its association with climate action engagement went up. We discuss these findings' theoretical and practical implications in detail below.

Theoretical implications

The (perceived) endorsement of biospheric values

Our findings on the (perceived) endorsement of biospheric values are highly consistent with the existing literature. As was found earlier^{3,4,29,48}, individuals very strongly endorsed biospheric values while perceiving national citizens to weaker endorse biospheric values. Individuals also perceived climate marchers to have strong biospheric values, which supports and extends previous findings which observed that other “green” groups were perceived to have strong biospheric values⁹. As our sample was aimed at being close to representative of the Dutch population, our findings suggest that there is indeed a strong personal value basis for climate action within Dutch society but that Dutch citizens substantially underestimate the extent to which other Dutch citizens endorse biospheric values^{4,8,11}. Whether perceptions about climate marchers are accurate is harder to evaluate since our sample has too few climate marchers to draw representative inferences about the value endorsement within that group.

Notably, our respondents reported that they endorsed biospheric values equally or more strongly than climate marchers, despite almost none of them attending the climate march. Attending a climate march is often portrayed as an act of above-average climate engagement, which may suggest that individuals overreport their own biospheric values or underestimate those of climate marchers. However, it could also be that the level of (perceived) value endorsement is accurate. Indeed, the climate march was attended by a wide diversity and large group of people, not only reflecting those extremely engaged. Moreover, many individuals who deeply care about climate change may not attend climate marchers, for instance, because of not being able to, regarding marches ineffective, or disliking mass gatherings, which was indeed what many respondents indicated on an open-ended question in our questionnaire.

Associations between (perceived) biospheric values and climate action

Our findings on the associations between (perceived) biospheric values and climate action engagement partly support earlier research and offer new and diverging perspectives. In line with earlier findings^{2,4,7,19}, stronger personal endorsement of biospheric values was consistently related to stronger engagement in climate action, with a medium-sized effect. Similarly, the more individuals perceived climate marchers to endorse biospheric values, the more they engaged in diverse climate actions, again with a medium-sized effect. This supports earlier findings that individuals act in line with both personal and perceived group values^{9,13,14,39}, each being (partly) uniquely related to climate action engagement; and extends earlier findings to a group that has not been studied in this light before, namely climate marchers.

It is noteworthy that we found a medium-sized association between perceived biospheric values of climate marchers and climate action engagement and that this effect remained stable when controlling for personal biospheric values. In most previous studies, the association between perceived biospheric values of others and climate action engagement was weak^{9,13,14,39} and substantially decreased or even disappeared when controlling for personal biospheric values^{13,39}. The size of the effects could even be considered more remarkable, considering that almost none of our respondents attended the climate march. This suggests that sharing values and opinions – instead of actually being together at the march

– is already a strong basis for group influences to occur, something which resonates with research on opinion-based groups^{51,52}. Interestingly, the notion that most respondents did not attend the march themselves may even explain the relatively strong effects we observed. Earlier studies mostly focused on groups to which individuals clearly belonged, and which are relatively often activated and salient (e.g., national citizens, classmates). Consequently, the values of those groups may already be internalised into individuals' personal values, possibly explaining why those groups' values do not have much (unique) influence anymore. This seems less likely for the group of climate marchers, which is – at least for most of our respondents – not often activated nor salient, and whose values have, therefore, not (yet) been internalised. This could potentially explain the relatively strong and unique association we observed. Further research could shed more light on when and how individuals are influenced by (in)groups and when group influences are likely most impactful.

Contrary to earlier studies^{9,39}, we did not observe that individuals who perceived national citizens to have stronger biospheric values engaged in more climate action. Instead, the more individuals perceived national citizens to endorse biospheric values, the less they generally engaged in climate action, although this effect was small, unstable and mostly occurred when controlling for personal biospheric values and the perceived biospheric values of climate marchers. Yet, this finding may have key implications for our reasoning as it implies that if one wants to promote climate action, underestimations of Dutch citizens' biospheric values do not need to be corrected, which exactly opposes what we proposed.

However, we argue that such conclusions are overly simplistic and should be nuanced. Specifically, groups may impact individuals differently over time, contingent upon the contexts in which a group is examined. Indeed, research on self-categorization shows that individuals sometimes act on one group membership, sometimes on another, and sometimes on their personal identity (i.e., what differentiates themselves from others), depending on which of these is most salient and relevant in a context^{53–55}. Moreover, research on identity signalling suggests that individuals are likely to align their actions with groups they evaluate as desirable while contrasting their actions away from groups they consider as undesirable^{30,31}. These evaluations, we argue, may fluctuate for the same group over time, causing individuals to sometimes act in line with a group's values, but to sometimes also contrast themselves away from them. For instance, whereas the group of national citizens may be somewhat desirable for many under neutral circumstances, this may swap around when it is made clear that too little climate action is taken at the national level, which is what a climate march could communicate. Accordingly, we believe that in the context of our study, the group of climate marchers was likely highly salient, relevant and – given individuals' strong caring about nature and the environment – desirable to most respondents, whilst the opposite applies to national citizens. This, we argue, could explain why individuals acted in line with the perceived biospheric values of climate marchers but opposed the perceived biospheric values of Dutch citizens in our study.

The idea that the influence of perceived values of groups on climate action may change over time and contexts is further corroborated by the finding that the perceived values of climate marchers were more

strongly associated with climate action engagement after the climate march than before. Specifically, having seen information on the actual march and the number and variety of people participating, with the march attracting substantially more people (40,000) than individuals anticipated (the median estimate was 10,000), likely made the group of climate marchers more salient, relevant, and desirable to the respondents and, therefore, more influential.

The ideas stated here about when and how perceived group values are associated with climate action need further testing but can have key implications for theory and practice. For instance, our reasoning implies that group influences may strongly fluctuate across contexts and time and that this should be considered when studying and reasoning about group influences. This may not only explain the differences we observed for perceived values of different groups and across time but also explain why perceived biospheric values of the same group have different effects across different studies^{9,38}. More practically, our reasoning implies that individuals may be motivated to act according to national citizens' values in later situations, at least when this identity is salient, relevant and attractive to them (e.g., during (inter)national elections, international comparisons). This would mean that correcting underestimations of Dutch citizens' biospheric values may – as we proposed in the introduction – still promote climate action in the longer run, even though interventions to correct perceived values may sometimes backfire at first.

Changes over the course of a climate march

We studied (perceived) biospheric values and climate action over the course of a climate march as we anticipated that the event could correct underestimations of Dutch citizens' biospheric values, which, according to earlier theorising, is key to promoting climate action (although following our above reasoning, most likely only in the long run)^{4,8}. In line with this, we indeed found that individuals perceived the biospheric values of Dutch citizens to be stronger after the climate march than before. This would promote climate action when individuals act in line with these values, which, according to previous studies (but not the current study), is often the case^{9,39}.

Interestingly, explorative analyses indicated that climate marchers were perceived to have slightly weaker biospheric values after the climate march. This decrease may be due to the march being more mainstream and less activist than most individuals beforehand anticipated, attracting more, and more diverse, people than they initially thought. Personal biospheric values remained relatively stable over time, which aligns with earlier theorising that defined personal values as stable constructs^{56,57}.

Interestingly, we did not find significant changes in climate action engagement over time. If anything, climate action engagement seemed to go down over the course of the climate march. Although we did not anticipate this beforehand, this finding does align with the earlier discussed associations between perceived biospheric values and climate action engagement, and the changes in these perceived values over time.

Potential limitations

We already argued that the associations between the perceived endorsement of biospheric values by different groups and climate action engagement might have been affected by the context and timeframe in which our data was collected. The short timeframe in which the T1 and T2 data were collected might also have limited our chances of obtaining (significant) differences over time. People often aim to be consistent in their answers and actions (i.e., self-consistency), and some changes are unrealistic to expect, particularly within a short amount of time. For instance, habitual behaviour (e.g., taking a car)⁵⁸ may take longer than a couple of weeks to change^{59,60}. Hence, it is quite likely that our conclusions on changes throughout the climate march are quite conservative and that larger impacts could have been obtained on other measures, after longer periods of time, or after repeated exposures, which future longitudinal research designs could test.

Another potential limitation of our study is that our T1 measurement was collected very close to the climate march, and that respondents were informed about the climate march in the T1 questionnaire, which may have impacted our results and conclusions. Specifically, the level of climate action engagement might have already been higher at T1 compared to more neutral situations in which individuals do not consider a climate march, meaning that the climate march might have promoted climate action but before we anticipated this to happen. In addition, all our respondents were (made) aware of the climate march, which impacts what can be concluded. Our results say something about changes and responses among people who are already (made) aware of a climate march, not necessarily what happens in society during a climate march, in which case many citizens are likely unaware of the march taking place. Yet, this does not mean that our results only apply to those who are typically aware of climate marches, as our sample was close to nationally representative, indicating that the observed effects apply to a wide population, including those typically unaware of marches.

Another limitation of our study is the lack of a true control group. Accordingly, we cannot draw causal inferences. Although unlikely, it might be that another event took place during our study that caused the associations we observed and differences over time. Future research with true experimental designs should unravel whether (awareness about) a climate march can indeed correct misperceptions of Dutch citizens' values and promote climate action, although we believe our findings provide promising initial evidence for this.

A more methodological limitation is that our measure of (perceived) biospheric values might have been prone to measurement errors, particularly for two reasons. First, we only used single items to measure (perceived) values. Single-item measures may be relatively strongly affected by random errors (e.g., by accidentally clicking on the wrong answering option) or misinterpretations, which inflate measurement errors. Second, our measure consisted of statements ("I / climate marchers / Dutch citizens find it extremely important in life to respect nature and protect the environment") on which respondents had to indicate their (dis)agreement, which may not fully capture the strength of (perceived) endorsement. To illustrate, one could "completely disagree" with the statement if they find respecting nature and protecting the environment not important at all, but also if they find it "important" but not "extremely important", potentially inducing measurement errors. Because of these limitations, we would advise

using another measure in the future. However, we have reason to be confident in our findings, specifically because (i) earlier research found our measure to be strongly correlated with more extensive, well-validated measures of biospheric values (Kelly et al., 2022) and (ii) the here observed means and distributions strongly overlapped with earlier studies using extensive well-validated measures^{4,7,9,14,24,28}. In addition, measurement errors like these typically reduce effect sizes and limit the chances of finding significant effects, so if measurement errors would indeed have been a problem, this most likely made our conclusions overly conservative⁶¹.

Two more general methodological limitations common to questionnaire studies might be important to consider. First, since all measures were self-reported by the same source in two questionnaires, there is a risk of common method variance. That is, the items might already be associated with each other due to being asked together in the same way and around the same time, even if they had little to do with each other. Although we tried to limit shared method variance by formulating questions in different ways (e.g., using different scales for different types of climate action engagement), asking questions about individuals themselves and different groups, and running analyses with multiple predictors, this might still have impacted some of our outcomes and is thus important to consider. Second, on various measures (e.g., personal values, perceived values of climate marchers), respondents scored relatively high, causing ceiling effects and limiting variation between respondents. This may have made it more difficult to observe differences between individuals and relationships between variables. To prevent this, future studies could frame such questions even more extremely or add scale points, although it is important to note that despite these potential limitations, we did observe clear support for most of our hypotheses.

Practical implications

Our study has important practical implications. It shows that personal biospheric values, and perceived biospheric values of climate marchers and Dutch citizens, are associated with individuals' climate actions and that perceptions about others' values can change during a climate march. These findings could be utilised in various ways by parties who aim to promote climate action, such as policymakers, NGOs, and climate activist groups.

Specifically, our results suggest that events and interventions can affect individuals' perceptions of the endorsement of biospheric values within different groups (e.g., national citizens, climate marchers), which may have downstream influences on the climate actions individuals take. We argue that in contexts where a group is relevant, salient and desirable, and in which behaviour change is possible, the strengthening of perceived biospheric values could promote climate action.

If one knows that a specific group is often relevant and salient in a given context (e.g., for employees, the company they are working for), it may thus be fruitful to make the desirable values of that group more salient (e.g., through communication and vision). Alternatively, interventions could strategically make groups with desirable values salient and relevant in certain contexts. When climate action is desired,

interventions could thus (i) communicate about the strong endorsement of biospheric values by groups that are often relevant, salient and desirable, and (ii) make groups that are already perceived as having strong biospheric values more salient, each of which could promote climate action.

Our study did not find an immediate increase in climate action engagement throughout a climate march. However, it is crucial to emphasise that such changes may occur in the long run. As discussed earlier, the perceived increase in the endorsement of biospheric values among national citizens may lead to stronger engagement in climate action in contexts where this group is salient and relevant compared to similar contexts before the climate march. Furthermore, climate marches likely influence not only citizens' perceptions about each other but also how policy- and decision-makers perceive national citizens. If a climate march leads policy- and decision-makers to perceive the endorsement of biospheric values in society as stronger, this could encourage them to implement the policies and system changes needed to address climate change and stimulate climate action.

Conclusion

We find that climate action engagement is stronger for individuals with stronger personal biospheric values, who perceive climate marchers to have stronger biospheric values, and who perceive Dutch citizens to have weaker biospheric values. In addition, we observed that most individuals have strong biospheric values and perceive climate marchers to have strong biospheric values but think that national citizens endorse these values substantially less than they do. Whereas personal biospheric values and the perceived biospheric values of climate marchers remained relatively stable throughout the climate march, individuals perceived national citizens to have clearly stronger biospheric values after the climate march took place. In other words, the climate march seemed to have partly corrected the widespread underestimation of national citizens' biospheric values. Although we did not observe these changes in perceived biospheric values to increase individual climate action engagement, we argue that these changes may increase climate action in the long run. Specifically, the changes may promote climate action in contexts where the group of national citizens is relevant, salient and desirable, and may stimulate policy and decision-makers to support individuals in taking climate action.

Declarations

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CRedit author contribution statement:

TB: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition

LS: Writing – Review & Editing, Conceptualization

Data Availability

The full questionnaires and the data used for this study are available https://osf.io/ducs7/?view_only=6825f47d7d524f0bae7427255651be2f

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Footnotes

1. We decided to analyse the full sample, including those respondents who attended the climate march, because (i) we wanted our sample to represent Dutch society (which includes climate marchers) and (ii) because the outcomes and conclusions of analyses of the datasets with and without climate marchers were very similar.
2. It is sometimes advised to use MRAT-adjusted scores instead of raw scores in regression analyses¹. MRAT-adjusted scores reflect the prioritisation of a value, calculated by subtracting the mean of all values from the score on a single value, for each individual. An advantage of the MRAT is that it corrects for scale use (i.e. a personal tendency to score high or low on scales), a disadvantage is that it does not account for the fact that people may also truly endorse values in general more or less than others, which information is lost through the MRAT-adjustment. Whether raw or MRAT-adjusted scores are more appropriate depends, in our opinion, on the aim of the study. In our case, we deem raw scores more appropriate because we are interested in the endorsement of biospheric values irrespective of the other values, and how these scores change over time and are associated with climate action engagement. Considering these aims, MRAT-adjusted scores are problematic since these do not capture whether a respondent's (perceptions of a) value changed, but whether its relative position compared to other values changed, which also happens when other than the focal variable change. For this reason, we decided to use raw instead of MRAT-adjusted scores in all our main analyses, which we also consider easier and more intuitive to interpret. We do report the main analyses using the MRAT-adjusted instead of raw scores in Appendix 1. Although effects for MRAT-adjusted scores are sometimes smaller, directions of associations and general conclusions do not differ between the methods used.